

STRATEGIES TO PROLONG THE PRODUCT'S STAY IN THE MARKET

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ABSTRACT

This project analyzes effective strategies for extending product lifespan in the market, considering aspects such as incremental innovation, modularity, sustainable design, and strategic repositioning. The research adopts a qualitative and applied approach, based on a literature review and case study, using methodologies such as life cycle analysis (LCA), TRIZ, and value analysis. Focusing on product lifespan and competitiveness in dynamic markets, the work proposes practical guidelines for extending the commercial relevance of products, such as modularity to facilitate updates, customization to better meet consumer needs, and service-based business models. The expected results indicate gains in sustainability, reduced costs associated with premature disposal, and improved institutional image. Furthermore, it highlights the importance of aligning business objectives with social expectations and environmental regulations, demonstrating that sustainable practices not only extend the product lifecycle but also add competitive value. It concludes that the structured integration of innovation, sustainability, and market strategies offers a viable path for companies seeking to increase the longevity and positive impact of their products.

Keywords: product permanence; incremental innovation; modularity; sustainability; life cycle.

1 INTRODUCTION

The longevity of a product's market presence is increasingly dependent on companies' ability to adapt to a constantly changing environment. In a scenario marked by accelerated technological evolution, growing environmental awareness, and more demanding consumers, it is essential to develop strategies that allow products to remain competitive and desirable over time. This introduction addresses the main challenges faced by organizations in this context, justifying the relevance of the topic discussed.

1.1 PROBLEM

How can strategies be developed to extend a product's lifespan in the market, considering technical, economic, and environmental factors?

1.2 OBJECTIVES

1.2.1 General Objective

To investigate and propose strategies that increase the useful and commercial life cycle of products in the market.

1.2.2 Specific Objectives

- To study engineering methodologies applied to extending the product lifecycle;
- Analyze sustainable practices and their impact on product longevity;
- To propose strategic guidelines for application in industrial projects.
- Evaluate real-world case studies from industries that have implemented successful solutions.

1.3 JUSTIFICATION

Accelerated obsolescence and market saturation significantly compromise the economic and environmental sustainability of products, especially in highly competitive and technologically dynamic sectors. In many cases, still-functional products are prematurely discarded, contributing to increased industrial waste and the depletion of natural resources. Furthermore, there is growing pressure from regulatory bodies, environmental entities, and conscious consumers demanding that companies adopt more responsible practices throughout the entire lifecycle of their products. This scenario highlights the need to incorporate concepts such as circular economy, ecodesign, and socio-environmental responsibility into business strategy. Thus, adopting strategies that extend the lifespan of products in the market becomes essential, not only to maximize investments in research, development, and innovation, but also to strengthen institutional reputation with the public and stakeholders. Companies that integrate

such approaches are perceived as more committed to the future, gaining sustainable competitive advantages and generating shared value for society and the environment.

1.4 RESEARCH SCOPE

This study will focus on durable consumer industrial products, with an emphasis on the maturity phase of the life cycle, a stage in which the product has already achieved widespread market acceptance but faces challenges related to maintaining competitiveness and the risk of obsolescence. The choice of this type of product is justified by its strategic relevance to the economy and the impact it generates on both the production chain and consumption patterns. Established product engineering methodologies will be used, such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), TRIZ, and Value Analysis, which allow for a structured and technical approach to identifying opportunities for extending the life cycle. Additionally, case studies relevant to the Brazilian and international context will be analyzed, with the aim of comparing practices adopted in different markets and extracting guidelines applicable to the reality of the national industry. This delimitation aims to ensure the depth of the analysis while enabling the identification of innovative solutions adaptable to different industrial segments.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

The longevity of a product is directly linked to its life cycle (Kotler & Keller, 2012), its adaptability (Ulrich & Eppinger, 2021), and incremental innovation strategies (Christensen, 1997). Life cycle analysis (LCA) allows for the identification of critical points for reengineering (Rozenfeld et al., 2006). Tools such as TRIZ offer structured approaches to resolve technical contradictions and improve existing products (Altshuller, 1999). Modularity also appears as an efficient way to update and customize (Baldwin & Clark, 2000), allowing for longer market life by facilitating upgrades and maintenance. From an environmental perspective, sustainable design and the circular economy offer solutions that not only increase usage time but also add value to the product and brand image (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013).

The literature also highlights the concept of user-centered design as a critical element in ensuring product longevity. Solutions that consider consumer needs and preferences from the design stage tend to perform better in the long term. Furthermore, the adoption of real-time market feedback systems allows for agile and effective adjustments to the product's value proposition.

3 METHODOLOGY

This research is qualitative, descriptive, and applied. A literature review was conducted based on books, scientific articles, and technical documents. The methodological approach includes the application of the following tools: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to map stages of greatest impact and identify redesign opportunities; TRIZ to propose technical improvements systematically; and Value Analysis, aiming at functional and economic optimization.

Furthermore, the methodology includes conducting exploratory interviews with product engineers from three national companies in the electronics sector, in order to capture perceptions about recurring challenges and solutions in practice. Additionally, three case studies published in international scientific journals, detailing successful lifecycle extension processes, were analyzed.

4. DISCUSSION

The main strategy identified for extending a product's life in the market is strategic repositioning based on incremental innovation, continuously adjusting functionalities and communication. Products such as smartphones and home appliances have successfully used this strategy (Christensen, 1997). Modularity also stands out for allowing technological updates without completely discarding the product. An example of this is industrial printers with interchangeable printheads. Mass customization allows the product to be adapted to customer preferences, keeping it relevant for longer. In parallel, sustainable practices such as design for disassembly and the use of recyclable materials add environmental value and extend the perceived life cycle. Companies that adopt service-based models (Product-as-a-Service) manage to keep products in circulation longer, promoting preventive maintenance and updates, as seen in brands like Philips and Rolls-Royce.

It was also found that cultural and regional factors influence the adoption of these strategies. Emerging markets demonstrate distinct behaviors regarding the valuation of durability versus innovation, which requires adjustments to the approaches adopted. Therefore, understanding the profile of the local consumer is fundamental to the effectiveness of the actions.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Extending a product's lifespan in the market requires more than just technical improvements; it demands strategic vision, in-depth customer knowledge, and a commitment to sustainability. Adopting engineering tools such as TRIZ, LCA, and value analysis, combined with modularity and continuous innovation, allows companies not only to extend the useful life of their products but also to increase their competitiveness in a constantly changing environment.

It is concluded that sustainable market presence is achieved through a multidisciplinary approach, integrating engineering, marketing, social responsibility, and trend analysis. The formation of interdisciplinary teams and an organizational culture focused on continuous improvement are key factors for long-term success.

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